

ECONOMETRIC MODEL OF BUSINESS PROCESS MANAGEMENT OF CRAFTS IN THE CONTEXT OF ECONOMIC DIGITALIZATION

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ABSTRACT

The theoretical foundations of the mechanisms for building an empirical model using digital technologies have been improved in the development of handicrafts. A mathematical apparatus for creating a complex numerical econometric model of the regional craft system has been developed.

In the world, great attention is paid to scientific research in improving the theoretical and methodological basis of digitalization of craft management, taking into account the processes of digital transformation in the field on the basis of an innovative approach to increasing the development of crafts using IT. Research on the management of handicrafts in rural areas of the world, research on the full use of opportunities in the use of information and communication technologies in this area. One of the most pressing issues today is new approaches to the development of handicrafts, their adaptation to new modern technical requirements, digitization of handicrafts in rural areas and harmonization with norms and quality standards using IT, especially in order to reduce poverty and improve living standards.

Well-known American scientist M. Drabenstott identified five challenges that are crucial in the socio-economic development of rural areas in the United States, one of the most developed countries in the world, but they also apply to many other cases:

Transition to digital technology.

Encouraging artisans.

Use of a new agro-industrial complex.

Improving human capital.

Rural environment support.

We can see that the concepts of "Digital Economy" put forward in the scientific work of "Digital Economy" introduced by D. Tepskott were put forward.

In our opinion, there are the following pressing issues in the development of handicrafts: defining the classification of handicrafts, assessing the

nature of handicrafts, developing a system of handicraft indicators in the current situation, improving the process of econometric modeling and forecasting of handicraft development.

It is known that as a result of the development of handicrafts, the country's gross domestic product will increase. This is done in the following directions: in the conditions of market relations, as a result of the development of handicrafts, a gross domestic product is created, whether or not material wealth is created.

In the modern era of development of handicrafts, it is gaining popularity. Therefore, the labor efficiency per unit of result achieved is required to be able to calculate fixed assets, material and financial costs.

Crafts have long been a part of human economic activity, social community life. It is the interaction of people as an institution of social community of craftsmen, the existence of useful activities - a necessary condition of human society and life.

It should be noted that it is no exaggeration to say that artisans increase the level of development of society not only at the level of its productive forces, but also taking into account the spiritual and enlightenment state.

In this study, we will define craft as a system by improving craft development models as a basis for systematic analysis. We consider both a single object and a type of craft to achieve a goal as a collection of collected elements. That is, we systematically study crafts. This craft being studied is understood as an interconnected whole in its integrity. As a result of systematic analysis, the cost-effectiveness indicator is determined.

If we consider the process as a system in the modeling of craft industries, we need to choose the main influencing factors, namely the input indicators. When modeling a process, we choose the type or appearance of the model to be created, whichever type of craft network we choose. Not all factors can be taken into account in modeling, so we must choose the main influencing factors and take into account the ongoing socio-economic reforms in the industry. The resulting factor and evaluation criteria are determined from the generated model.

In a market economy, crafts operate in different forms of ownership, full economic independence and competitiveness. This market involves the flexible use of different methods of management and the choice of econometric models of service that allow for rapid adaptation to changes in the external environment in a competitive environment.

Our goal is to analyze the service sector in the region and improve its models.

In a market economy, service enterprises operate in a variety of forms of ownership, full economic independence and competitiveness. This market involves the flexible use of different methods of management and the choice of econometric models of service that allow for rapid adaptation to changes in the external environment in a competitive environment.

It is expedient to study whether the factors influencing social phenomena correspond to different values, not the same, and that their interdependence is correlated. Because the characteristic feature of social spheres is that it is impossible to determine the complete list

(strength) of all the factors influencing this sphere.

In addition, only approximate expressions of connections can be written using the formula. Because the number of factors influencing the living conditions of the population is so large, it is impossible to determine a complete list of them and write an equation that fully expresses the relationship to the resulting outcome sign.

The development of the living conditions of the population is so incompletely correlated that each value of the factors corresponds to different values of the results of the factor influencing the different time and space. Hence, the exact number of influencing factors will be unknown. It is expedient to study such a relationship through correlation links.

Our task is to assess the presence of strong and weak links that affect the development of public service networks. We use the correlation analysis method to accomplish this task. Because our goal is to assess the importance and reliability of the interdependencies that affect the development of each sector that serves the population. Through correlation analysis, we measure the degree of dependence that affects the living standards of the

population, but we cannot determine the cause of the relationship.

We selected information for the reporting years 2005 - 2021, which identified areas of service and the factors affecting them on the basis of certain characteristics

At the same time, the factors influencing the development of handicrafts are highlighted in modeling. Selected factors may be involved in modeling once or more. Because we look at one factor as the main influencing factor.

Conclusion

Econometric modeling of handicrafts is expedient. Crafts development has a positive impact on the development of another industry.

Therefore, the use of econometric models in the form of a system of interconnected equations is of particular importance in the development of crafts. In addition, the organizational-economic mechanism of craft development represents a hierarchical system of interconnected elements and groups (subjects, objects, principles, forms, methods and tools) at different levels, as well as their interrelationships, innovative infrastructure, forms relationships with market participants.

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